

THEME: INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

This article explores the role of information technology in education, the quality of lessons and the interest of young people in the field of IT through the use of information technology in the classroom, as well as the advantages of multimedia in education.

Key words: Information, communication, technology, audio signal, video signal, multimedia, individual, motivation, computer, informatics

The modern world level of development of information and communication technologies is such that the establishment of a national system in the country in accordance with the integration of the infrastructure of the global information space and the national information network is an important factor in the effectiveness of national economy, management, science and education. These problems are very complex and at the same time relevant for our country. Education can be obtained from anywhere in the world, using the opportunities of modern information and communication technologies (ICT). Although traditional education has retained its status, distance learning technologies have become more popular in recent years.

Today, our country is building an education system aimed at integrating into the new global information and educational environment. This is accompanied by significant changes in the organization of the educational process in line with modern technical capabilities. The introduction of modern information technologies in the field of education allows to qualitatively simplify and change the methods of teaching and the organization of the teaching process on the basis of a new approach. Information and communication technologies are an important part of the modernization of the education system. ICT is a method of processing information with various hardware and software devices. It is, first and foremost, computers with the necessary software and telecommunications facilities with data.

The 1st article of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", adopted on August 29, 1997, defines the legal basis for education, vocational training of citizens and the constitutional right of everyone to education. It was emphasized that, nowadays, there is a great need for new requirements for education. The use and management of distance learning technologies in the educational process also play an important role. In this regard, a number of urgent work is being carried out in the Republic.

Since 2012, a single videoconferencing educational technology has been implemented among all higher education institutions (HEIs) of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and now a lot of attention is paid to e-learning. At the same time, planned work is underway to open new opportunities and prospects for universities. An example of this is the remote management of human resources in the regions. The new phase of e-learning or distance learning involves not only the use of information technology, but also the provision of e-learning resources.

Electronic and distance technologies are options for education that use information and communication technologies.

E-Learning - Previously, the term "e-learning" was understood as computer-assisted learning, but with the development of information technology, this concept has expanded. Today, e-learning covers many educational technologies, which can be divided into two types, synchronous and asynchronous.

Simultaneous e-learning is distance learning, but it is real-time learning. It's like a full-time course, except that the participants are far apart. Webinars are one of the brightest forms of this form of education. Special softwares are used to organize lectures.

Asynchronous e-learning is when a student receives all the necessary information from online sources or electronic media (CDs, DVDs or flash cards) and independently organizes the pace and schedule of learning. The asynchronous e-learning system includes all types of CD courses and e-learning courses, ostcasts and screencasts. Today, e-learning has become an integral part of the educational process in many universities. It has also been involved in the organization of training courses, some corporations have branches, whose task is to organize e-courses for employees.

Distance learning is a broader concept than E-Learning. It is an intensive counseling synthesis of interactive independent learning and support. Thus, e-learning is part of distance learning. Distance education provides students with basic learning materials and interactive interaction between student and teacher

during the learning process. The manuals can be delivered without a computer or the Internet.

Advantages of distance learning

There are many benefits to using distance learning. These are some of them:

Opportunity to study from home - People living in remote villages do not always have the opportunity to go to the big cities and go to university. Distance learning technologies allow them to study without leaving their hometown.

Studying and working simultaneously - students will have the opportunity to study without leaving work. This is especially useful for advanced training or secondary education.

Acquisition of the quality study technology and curriculum - a student can receive quality teaching materials, communicate with the teacher and create their own individual curriculum.

Impartiality of assessment - distance learning technology involves continuous monitoring of the quality of knowledge, evaluation of results, objective automated assessment that is free of human factors, loss of material interest in the field.

An individual approach to learning - a combination of changing schedules, work and study, as well as adapting the material to the speed of individual learning, makes distance learning accessible to all.

The modern humanities academy is one of the leaders in distance education. It is an innovative HEI that provides students in different parts of the world with quality e-learning at affordable prices without having to change their lifestyle.

Keeping up with innovations

The Modern Humanities Academy (MHA) was founded on November 23, 1992. Today it is the largest university in Russia and Europe, with about 100 students. Within 22 years, more than 300,000 students have graduated from higher education. The academy currently offers many educational programs:

Bachelor's degree programs: ("Linguistics", "Jurisprudence", "Management", "Economics", "Computer Science and VT", "Psychology", "Philosophy", "Pedagogical Education", "Political Science", "Sociology", "History of Art", "Commerce", "Social Affairs", "State and local government");

• Specialties: ("Taxes and taxation", "Translation and translation studies", "Social work");

• Master's degree programs (Jurisprudence, Economics, Management, Informatics and VT, Philosophy, Psychology, Personnel Management, Public and Local Administration).

Specialties of secondary special education:

- On specialties of secondary special education - training of specialists of secondary level ("Economics and accounting (by industry)", "Management (by industry)", "Law").
- The MHA is, in fact, the only university in the field of secondary special education that not only uses the principles of E-Learning, but also creates completely new educational products.

Distance learning technology

The MHA has introduced a wide range of tools into the e-learning environment. These include: lectures, supertutors, logic diagrams, adaptive test-trainings, test and evaluation programs. MHAs are organizational didactic robots that create individual work plans for employees, train, evaluate, monitor plan implementation, perform financial calculations, and generate rating books.

Access to e-learning resources is provided through the student's "Personal Studio" on the site. The administration of the educational process is carried out through the intellectual information system IIS "Nur". The system tracks and monitors each student's enrollment from entering to graduation, and electronically identifies the student in assessment and academic administration. If we introduce the above-mentioned systems based on improved principles in all levels of educational institutions of the country, I think it will be part of the exemplary, effective implementation of reforms in the educational process.

References

1. Decree F-4947 "On the Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
2. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. Tashkent evening. January 25, 2020. № 13 (14064).
3. SS Gulomov and others. Information Systems and Technologies: A Textbook for University Students / Edited by Academician SS Gulomov. - T., «Sharq», 2000.
4. www.lex.uz
5. www.ziyonet.uz